

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

DEEP-SEA MINING AND THE RESPONSIBILITY OF INTERNATIONAL PLAYERS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL PRESERVATION.

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POLICY STATEMENT

The nascent deep-sea mining industry aims to remove minerals from the ocean floor, such as precious metals, especially those considered critical for sectors such as the energy transition. The practice involves using specialized equipment and technologies to reach great depths in the ocean. However, while it would meet certain countries' industrial, technological, and infrastructure demands, it opens up a profound debate regarding its long-term environmental impacts, regulation, and inspection. Thus, international actors come together at the International Seabed Authority (ISA) to outline rumors of activity and defend different agendas. In this Policy Brief, we bring the debate to offshore mining, focusing on the role played by ISA and other agents and the advances and setbacks towards adopting the Mining Code for the ocean floor under International Waters.

BACKGROUND

The meeting of the Assembly of the International Seabed Authority (ISA), completed in July, comprised three weeks of negotiations on deep-sea mining, in which no progress was recorded in the adoption or even completion of the drafting of a Mining Code for the seabed below International Waters. Despite the failure, the Assembly meeting led to the announcement of opposition to the activity by five more countries, including Brazil.

The urgency to adopt a Code was due to a request made by the Republic of Nauru through *Nauru Ocean Resources Incorporated* (NORI), a subsidiary of the Canadian *The Metals Company* (TMC). Based on a provision in the Annex to the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS, in English), the request began a two-year period in July 2021. At the end of the period, it was anticipated that work plans could be submitted for consideration by the ISA Council in light of any regulations in force. However, during the time that has elapsed, the Authority has not completed the requested work, primarily due to limitations on face-to-face meetings resulting from the security measures necessary to overcome the COVID-19 pandemic. For the first time since the creation of the ISA, the discussion on a pause or moratorium on deep-sea mining was on the agenda of the Assembly, the supreme body of the

authority that represents all 168 Member States and which would have the power to carry out ocean-protection measures that would prevent deep-sea mining. The discussion, blocked by China, also encountered resistance from more governments interested in the activity, such as Russia and South Korea. As countries with consolidated mining and refining industrial bases, the movement to move forward in the search for alternatives for obtaining mineral resources with high environmental costs.

Governments advocating a precautionary pause or implementation of a moratorium on seabed mining are Germany, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain, Fiji, Finland, Ireland, Micronesia, New Zealand, Palau, Panama, Portugal, Dominican Republic, Samoa, Sweden, Switzerland, and Vanuatu. France also belongs to the group since its government defends an unrestricted ban on the activityⁱⁱ. Furthermore, the theme gains momentum with the progress in drafting the United Nations Treaty for the High Seas, which deals with biodiversity beyond national jurisdictions.

Despite the end of the stipulated deadline, the Authority decided not to consider plans for commercial exploration until 2024, when it is expected to have made more significant progress in drafting the Code. However, the legal loophole that would allow a company to apply for a mineral exploration contract remains open even in the absence of regulation.

Countries' positions against deep-sea mining:

Moratorium	Precautionary pause	Ban
Fiji, Palau, Samoa (june/2022)	Chile, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain (july/2022)	France (november/2022)
Micronesia (july/2022)	Germany, Panama (november/2022)	
New Zealand (october/2022)	Vanuatu, Dominican Republic (march/2023)	
Switzerland (june/2023)	Sweden(june/2023)	
Canada (july/2023)	Switzerland, Brazil, Finland, Portugal (july/2023)	

Source: *Deep Sea Conservation Coalition, 2023.*

FINDINGS

The International Energy Agency (IEA) is preparing for its first conference dedicated to non-energy minerals, to be held on September 28, 2023. These, necessary for the production chains of equipment generating energy considered clean, are geographically dispersed in the Earth's crust and have their extraction and refining concentrated in a few international companies (GASPAR FILHO and SANTOS, 2022). As a preparatory document for the event to be hosted in Paris, the IEA published the report "Critical Minerals Market Review 2023". It is important to note that throughout its 83 pages, there is no mention of seabed mining, offshore mining, deep-sea mining, or any other synonyms. This observation becomes relevant when we point out that there is a section dedicated to trends in the markets for critical minerals that do not consider obtaining them outside the countries' coasts.

Therefore, the urgency with which companies in the mining sector address the issue is questioned, seeking to suggest the need to mine the oceans to supplement production chains. Such a speculative movement encounters resistance in sectors of the Academy and even in the market potentially interested in the supply of metals for batteries, for example. This is the case of companies like BMW, Volvo, and Renault. Although only seven European countries have spoken out against offshore mining, it is noted that the European Union, as a bloc (and member of the ISA), is currently against the activity. The position may be momentary, considering the funds invested to date in research in the sector at a regional level - more than €80 million in funding from the European Commission (JONES, 2023).

In Academia, opposition to offshore mining finds support in different fields of knowledge. The environmental impacts arising from the activity are the subject of study in areas of Natural Sciences such as Oceanography, Marine Biology, and Climatology. In Applied Social Sciences, we highlight a recent field of study called Blue Degrowth, an offshoot of the Degrowth trend of the 1970s. In this context, expanding productive and extractive frontiers into the oceans is criticized as a new space to suffer the consequences of human activities. Theorists such as Maria Hadjimichael (2018) point out the unsustainability of maintaining growth rates in countries' economies and the centralization of GDP in economic debates. In this way, this vision of the economy is connected to the exploration of marine resources, seeing efforts to obtain minerals from the ocean floor as an attempt to meet an insatiable demand for finite resources.

Parallel to the debate on the extraction of mineral resources under international waters, there are projects from countries that focus on obtaining minerals in their Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ). Currently, the metals closest to being extracted in this way are on the Norwegian continental shelf. Norway, which does not have claims for the exploration or exploitation of minerals with the ISA, plans to start mining in an area of up to 281,000km² (about the size of Italy) in its EEZ. Its Parliament will vote on the project in 2023, with activity beginning soon after (JONES, 2023).

The search for offshore minerals is part of a broader movement related to reducing external dependence on the supply of minerals considered critical. As countries transition to new energy sources, there is an emerging risk of creating new external dependencies to obtain minerals essential for generating renewable energy. This is because few countries and companies are responsible for most of the extraction and refining of these metals, as well as for manufacturing equipment such as wind turbines and solar panels (GASPAR FILHO and SANTOS, 2022).

In this way, different documents were published by international actors such as the United States, the European Union, Japan, and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). The texts focus on perspectives for the mineral sector according to the goals for the energy transition and how supply must be adapted to consumption expectations to achieve the decarbonization goals assumed in different treaties. Strategies published by the US focus on increasing the resilience of the national mineral market to reduce dependence on its most significant strategic adversary, China. The Asian country, in turn, is the largest international mineral producer and refiner (GASPAR FILHO and SANTOS, 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

In July, the International Seabed Authority (ISA) Assembly meeting recorded no progress in adopting the Mining Code for the seabed in International Waters. Despite this, five countries, including Brazil, announced their opposition to the activity. The urgency of the Code resulted from a request from the Republic of Nauru via *Nauru Ocean Resources Incorporated* (NORI), a subsidiary of Canadian *The Metals Company* (TMC), starting two years in July 2021. However, the Authority has not had success in completing the essay. For the first time, the discussion of a pause in deep-sea mining was on the ISA's agenda, meeting resistance from China, Russia, and South Korea, countries interested in supplying their mining industries. Countries such as Germany, Brazil, Canada, Chile, Costa Rica, Ecuador, Spain, France, and others advocate a pause or moratorium on seabed mining, considering more sustainable alternatives. Despite the deadline extension until 2024 by ISA, the legal loophole for companies to apply for mineral exploration contracts remains open. The search for deep-sea minerals aims to reduce external dependence on critical minerals for renewable energy. On the international scene, strategies are developed to deal with critical minerals and reduce environmental impacts throughout the production chain. It is crucial to preserve the oceans and consider the impacts of large-scale mining on the ocean floor. The ISA may choose not to allow work plans for mineral exploration via a moratorium or precautionary pause. Governments opposed to offshore mining, such as Brazil, must disseminate scientific knowledge about its impacts and play a central role in ocean conservation in international forums.

RECOMMENDATIONS

At the meeting at the International Energy Agency on September 28, different measures are expected to be proposed to better use terrestrial mineral resources and improve their recycling. Extending the life cycle of products can guarantee the prospect of reducing production to achieve adequate sustainability levels without considering obtaining minerals from the ocean floor.

The stability of economic growth as the ultimate objective of the Nation's policy is compromised by the finite nature of natural resources.

- (i) Carrying out an energy transition to maintain existing growth rates in economies previously based on fossil fuels could lead to new forms of environmental destruction beyond the carbon emissions currently being tackled. The analysis of the entire production chain of equipment that generates clean energy must prioritize the reduction of environmental impacts resulting from all stages involved.

While discussing mining seabeds based on the text of UNCLOS, one must

- (ii) remember the positive principle in the body of the Convention that defines the Area (the ocean floor beyond national jurisdictions) as a Common Heritage of Humanity. The extent of 54% of the oceans, which constitute the Area, can be explored, according to UNCLOS, only for the benefit of Humanity as a whole. The forecast in the Convention must be read considering the best knowledge available each time. The understanding of the impacts of human activities in 1982, when it was signed, was objectively lower than today. Appreciating the growing resistance to the expansion of productive frontiers by sectors of Academia and society focused on environmental preservation, decisions must be taken in the field of mining that avoid disturbing pristine environments with potentially irreversible impacts.

The International Seabed Authority is responsible for preserving the integrity of the oceans. It is up to the countries that constitute it to

- (iii) soberly recognize the little knowledge available about the impacts potentially resulting from large-scale mining activities on the ocean floor. As a reflection of the will of governments, which are increasingly speaking out against the mining of seabeds, the ISA can make the right decision not to allow work plans to be accepted through a moratorium, precautionary pause, or absolute ban.

Those countries that took the opposite position to the beginning of the mining industry on ocean floors are transparent that the exploration of new territories can lead to new environmental impacts. It is the responsibility of the governments that have expressed this position, such as the Brazilian,

(iv) to disseminate the best available scientific knowledge about the activity in different spheres of dialogue so that new meetings of the ISA Assembly have more significant support for opposing measures.

The traditional role of Brazilian diplomacy in the various climate conferences, capable of articulating objectives and commitments of countries at different stages of development, could become central to the preservation of the oceans. By expressing the position of defending a pause in offshore mining, the Brazilian government is faced with the opportunity to consolidate its position as a spokesperson for the conservation of the ocean floor in different spaces of international dialogue.

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ⁱⁱ Even though the country has exploration (research) contracts for polymetallic nodules in the Clarion Clipperton Zone (in the Pacific Ocean) and another for polymetallic sulfides in the Mid-Atlantic Ridge granted by ISA in 2001 and 2014, respectively.